

Challenges Faced by Women in the Non- Traditional Jobs

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Abstract

In the present world, Women no longer lag behind in career. Every family in India is looking out for ways and means of increasing the household because of the increasing cost of living, education expenses of children, housing properties etc. They take up both traditional as well as nontraditional jobs. Nontraditional jobs like architecture, computer programmers, computer software, hardware engineers, construction business etc. The US Department of labor defines a nontraditional career for women as one in which 25% or less of those employed in the field are women (US dept of labor, women’s bureau). They are expected to multitasking. They have to take care of the family and household even if they are working by virtue of their sex the man has stereotyped her as a submissive person of the society. She is also supposed to maintain her dignity and modesty in our society. Her non-cooperative husband can always overpower her. In the workplace she is considered less productive than her male counter parts. There are also issues related to remuneration, leave, health, and sexual harassment. In this backdrop the objective of the study is to find out the challenges faced by these women in combining job and household The research is planned to be conducted in Chennai after finalizing the Questionnaire.

The focus of the research is to identify problems faced

- 1. Support of parents and relatives*
- 2. Challenges faced by these women*
- 3. Cooperation from husbands*
- 4. Childcare*
- 5. Personal life*
- 6. Social life*
- 7. Managing home and career*
- 8. Salary and promotion system*

The policy implication and the recommendations would be given with the findings revealed.

Keywords: Traditional jobs, Non-traditional jobs, Career, Multitasking, and Sexual harassment.

Introduction

“Women makes a home into home” because the home has always been her preference, by showering her love care to children, husband and whole family with devotion and hard work. This is an accepted fact and a concrete truth of man’s life. But today the fact is hardly recognized as women have started to step out home to work.

Women no longer lag behind in career. Every family in India is looking out for ways and means of increasing the household because of the increasing cost of living, education expenses of children, housing properties etc. They take up both traditional as well as nontraditional jobs.

“Traditional or female-dominated occupations are those in which women represent 75 percent or more of total employed. Occupations include those with a sample size of at least 50,000 people employed. Total number of workers and women as a percentage of total employed are 2014 annual averages for all people employed (includes part-time and self-employed). (<http://www.bls.gov/cps/cpsaat11.htm> -)* Median weekly earnings are 2014 annual averages based on full-time wage and salary workers only. (<http://www.bls.gov/cps/cpsaat39.htm> Source: Bureau of Labor Statistics, Current Population Survey)”

“The U.S. Department of Labor defines a non-traditional career for women as one in which 25% or less of those employed in the field are women (Nontraditional Occupations for Women. U.S. Department of Labor, Women’s Bureau).” Any occupation in which women make up 25 percent or less of the total workforce is considered “non traditional”. In 1997, only 5.7% of all working women were employed in nontraditional jobs.” (Women’s Bureau, U.S. Department of Labor, Non-Traditional Occupations.):

Here are some examples of nontraditional jobs for women: architects, computer programmers, computer software and hardware engineers, detectives, chefs, barbers, clergy, engineers, computer and office machine repairers, construction and building inspectors, railroad conductors, machinists, truck drivers, fire fighters, aircraft pilots, and construction occupations. (Women’s Bureau, U.S. Department of Labor, Non-Traditional Occupations.):

In 21st century ,the department of labor lists over 100 occupations that fall into this category, among them is police officer and architect. The first female police officer was appointed in Los Angeles a century ago Louise Blanchard Bethune and first female architect appointed Louise Blanchard Bethune before 130 years (Companion to Women in the Workplace by Dorothy Schneider and Carl F. Schneider, ABC-CLIO, Inc., 1993).

US Department of labor , statistics in 2017, (the Median Weekly)says that women were low in number in occupations-construction trades and STEM ((Science, Technology, Engineering, and Math) fields.(Dawn Rosenberg Mckay updated November 16, 2018)

Characteristics of Nontraditional Occupations

Women choose Nontraditional jobs for various reasons. A survey conducted by Schroedel (1998), when questioned what attracted women to take up non traditional jobs 72 percent of them said was “the money.” which was not surprising because of the fact that women work for wages. (Florida State Department of Education, 1998). About twenty four percent said that the among the reason for choosing that job was doing something with their hands , to work outdoors and satisfaction of creativity. It also shows that with this job they are able to support their family. These are “the characteristics of successful women in nontraditional jobs are the following

- Love of learning
- Willingness to take on new challenges
- Interest in working with one’s hands
- Interest in seeing concrete products of one’s work
- Desire to earn higher wages and benefits (Workplace Solutions, 1998)
- In good physical health and fitness
- Need to earn more that \$6.00 per hour for self and family
- Need access to health care and other benefits 48
- Willingness to explore new things, new places, new people (Illinois Women in the Careers, 1998).”

Background of Women Entering Into Work Force

In the past before 1940, women had been working at home doing household chores like cooking, washing, taking care of children and family. They also involved themselves in farming during harvesting, they did canning, butter making and processing grain “All were in equal status to their employers, and often shared bedrooms and even beds with members of the family for whom they worked” (Baxadal & Gordon, 1995, p.22).

Slowly women started taking up office jobs which required women to complete high school and the most privileged took up college education (In 1920, 28,000 females attended college or 7.6 % of all females) (Baxadal & Gordon, 1995, p.22). These women who attended college remained single, took up managerial and professional jobs and especially social work, nursing and teaching. Females stayed employed only till they got married.

All through 1940, jobs were created for which first only men were employed and then women. “In 1941, the Volee Aircraft hired 25 females in California fourteen in Massachusetts (Coleman, 1995). Even when women made a breakthrough many of the firms did not take in women. Men also felt that “females did not have the physical strength, mechanical ability, and emotional stability to do high paying, skilled factory jobs. In addition, employers said the presence of females would distract them (Coleman, 1995).” Women who were married were prohibited from getting jobs in non-traditional areas. Teachers were rebuked if they were married and study shows that there were limits for married women to work for banks and insurance companies.

At the same time during World War II Women were hired in more numbers by department of labor. A lot of communal agencies worked on encouraging the employment of women. Many changes took place in the economic development.

“A ten minute film was shown to females about “Women in Defense” written by Eleanor Roosevelt, narrated by actress Katherine Hepburn. The film highlighted careers in areas such as a scientist, a factory worker, a modern pioneer, and a Red Cross volunteer, just to name a few. Mary Anderson from the Department of Labor and head of the Women’s Bureau announced that she “worked at establishing job training programs for females. Through the National Youth Administration (NYA), a program set up during the Great Depression to help unemployed youth, twenty thousand females were learning such skills as welding and radio repair” (Coleman, 1995).

World War II brought about many changes in employment of women in skilled jobs and industry. “Women worked in shipyards, lumber mills and steel mills. They worked as welders, mechanics, electricians and boilermakers, operated streetcars, buses, cranes, and tractors. In addition, women worked as engineers in the drafting rooms and physicists in industrial laboratories (Coleman, 1995). Women also became role models as police officers, taxicab drivers, lawyers, statisticians, journalists, and members of symphony orchestras (Weatherford, 2004)” A number of women worked as air raid wardens, fire watchers, police and auxiliary drivers. Women also took up confronting jobs and devoted hours flipping through the sky for enemy planes.

In 1945 world war ended leaving women out of jobs. Women were more patriotic and loyal in their work. Coleman 1995 quotes that many women and men wrote of the achievements, victories, the employment records of world war II in magazines, newspapers, spoke on radio programs, had contribution of posters and pamphlets. It was at this time women broke through the barriers and advanced to the occasion and proved that they could succeed in careers once considered as non-traditional for women.

Literature Review

The study on Understanding The Challenges Of Women In Non-traditional Occupations by Govinda Kumar Shrestha was based on understanding the women in nontraditional jobs in

Nepalese context this was a qualitative case study which was conducted from Kathmandu valley. The participants were seven of them who took up nontraditional occupations like Electrical, motorcycle mechanics, light vehicle driving and mechanical lathe operator. Data was collected using interviews and group discussion. Findings showed that Nepalese women who took up jobs in nontraditional sectors were in very small numbers which was due to the conventional thinking towards women that they should do only domestic work. It has not been women friendly to work in nontraditional jobs for these women. The Society does not believe these Women. People and society behave with suspicion towards these people. People also indulge in leg pulling and back biting towards these women but they get the support from their family and organization they also motivate and continue their work.

A Research project on women in nontraditional occupation-construction industry was conducted by Washborne gale Andrew 1994 which focuses on issues related to the women in construction field and gives the conclusions. It represents the problem of construction workers with statistical evidence it states conclusion and suggestions for practicing.

Women in Nontraditional Careers by Teresa A. Roche (2006) shows that in a construction and automotive technology which is dominated by male artificial barriers and attitudes prevent women from reaching their full potential. Study also shows that the late entrance of women in these industries shows very few role models for people. It has created a profile for nontraditional females. The study also reveals that women experienced obstacles due to disparity among male and female, acknowledgement from companions, society, and problems in managing both family and career.

Study Objectives

There has been a good number of studies on working women. As women became educated they started to take up traditional and non traditional jobs. Women are encouraged to take up traditional jobs. They do not motivate their children to select nontraditional jobs because of the risk they involve, no knowledge regarding the job and also parents want their children to be safe.

Women face a number of challenges in these jobs The objective of the was to examine the challenges faced by women working in nontraditional jobs like

- Doing household chores
- Taking care of children
- Support from husband, parents and relatives
- Personal life
- Social life
- Discrepancies in salary
- Promotion system
- Able to manage both home and career

Methodology

According to Sam Malhotra. (Essay on Home and the Working Woman by Sam Malhotra.). Women after educating and going for a job start neglecting the home because she not only has any energy to work at home after a long day work, which is a genuine cause. She also is losing concern in the home front. This attitude of women gives rise to many problems at home, with children and also with elders in the family. This has led to the study on these women in nontraditional career.

This study was conducted in Chennai on women working in nontraditional jobs. About 50 computer operators were taken as the sample (25 from SRM Institute of technology and 25 from Tamil Nadu Veterinary And Animal Sciences University. A questionnaire was drafted with 30 questions under the following heads

Doing household chores
Taking care of children
Support from husband, parents and relatives
Personal life
Social life
Discrepancies in salary
Promotion system
Able to manage both home and career
Relationship with male colleagues.
Questionnaire was also substituted with Interviews where ever possible.
Definitions

The U.S. Department of Labor defines a non-traditional career for women as one in which 25% or less of those employed in the field are women (Nontraditional Occupations for Women. U.S. Department of Labor, Women's Bureau).

Any occupation in which women make up 25 percent or less of the total workforce is considered "nontraditional". Women (Nontraditional Occupations for Women. U.S. Department of Labor, Women's Bureau).

some examples of nontraditional jobs for women: architects, computer programmers, computer software and hardware engineers, detectives, chefs, barbers, clergy, engineers, computer and office machine repairers, construction and building inspectors, railroad conductors, machinists, truck drivers, fire fighters, aircraft pilots, and construction occupations women (Nontraditional Occupations for Women. U.S. Department of Labor, Women's Bureau).

Analysis and Discussion

This study shows that among the total sample, 60 percent of them stay in nuclear family .All of them were confident in managing both family and career.

When asked about household chores 100 percent of them said that they cooked the food all alone but some were helped by their mother in laws in cutting vegetables. Only 10 percent of the were helped by husbands in cooking and cutting vegetables. For washing clothes all of them had washing machines. They arranged maids to help them in cleaning utensils and house. Surprisingly 10 percent of husbands helped them to keep house clean. Women by practice are trained to take care of cooking and home. These Women also get the support of husbands and in-laws whenever they need.

90 percent of these women work for 8-9 hours in the office. Only 10 percent work more than 10 hours. This is because of their seniority and completion of 10 years of service. Unlike the attitude of common people, all of these women help their children in their studies.90 percent of them help them to have their bath, dress up, have their breakfast, pack up their lunch bags They are helped by Auto men and some by husbands and others by school buses to be dropped and picked up from school. Children are taken care by their fathers or grandmothers in absence of their mother.

With regard to work about 90 percent of them do not take up extra work and also don't go out on official on duty. The reason being to take care of children and family. Male colleagues support and help them whenever they have doubt clarify them. None of the samples spoke about sexual harassment or misbehavior from male colleagues. But in the private sector they felt that there is a discrimination in the salary and promotion. Some felt that even after 6 year of service they were not given they were not given an increase in the salary and they were also not considered for promotion.

As the study was done on women who were e under 40 yrs none had any health issues. Even when they had slight health problems their husbands and in-laws took care of them.

Regarding their social life all of them attended birthday parties, functions and visited relatives and friends during holidays. They also occasionally went out during weekends.

Since the sample consisted only of computer operators the problems faced by them was veryless they were able to manage both home and career with the help of mother in law and husband. Took care of children, devoted time in social activities.

Conclusion

When women who are complete their education plan out their career they are not allowed to follow their dreams when it is not traditional. Women are not encouraged to take up jobs in technology, science, and security. Women are asked if they have brains or stamina to perform.

In my opinion women may take up the nontraditional jobs because of the benefits and the happiness it gives to pursue their dreams. These are some steps which should be taken

1. Women need to possess the skill and the training for the job .
2. They need to have a good health and stamina which is important for jobs like, engineers, computer and office machine repairers, construction and building inspectors, railroad conductors, machinists, truck drivers, fire fighters, aircraft pilots, and construction occupations.
3. They need training to manage the male colleagues. As they have to fight against sexual harassment and sexual crimes against them.
4. The society has not accepted women in nontraditional careers hence they need mental strength to convince people's criticism.
5. need to organize their work in both home and career.
6. fight or convince against salary discrimination due to her gender.
7. needs to work on continuous improvement in the career.

Scope For Further Study

Research can be conducted on

1. Challenges of working women
2. Challenges of working women who are single parents
3. Challenges of women working in private sectors.
4. Challenges of women women working in private sectors sectors
5. Challenges of women working in schools
6. Challenges of women working in Engineering colleges.
7. Challenges of women working in arts and science colleges.

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